

Critical Analysis of Effects of the Youth Health Application and Flipcharts on Adolescents' Knowledge about Early Marriage: A Quasi-Experiment Study

Letter to Editor:

With great interest, I have read the research article titled "effects of the Youth health application and flipcharts on adolescents knowledge about early marriage: a quasi-experiment study" (1). I appreciate the efforts of the authors in conducting this study, but I have a few concerns. In the introduction section, although the study aim has been stated, the specific objectives of the study were missing. Aims and objectives are important aspects of any research and should be clearly stated. Moreover, in the methods section, the author stated that 60 eligible females had participated in the study and 30 females were allocated in the intervention group and 30 females were allocated in the control group; however, there is very much difference in the data given in table 1. They represented that 6 subjects in the intervention group and 12 subjects in the control group were male. This is a great doubt I came across, because if the study is on females only, then what is the need of mentioning male numbers in the characteristics of respondents? Furthermore, the data on other characteristics of research respondents mentioned in the table is not homogenous; there are many differences in the numbers (%) in both the intervention and control groups. Next, the sampling method adopted is confusing because the authors stated that females were selected through convenience sampling methods, but randomization was mentioned in the CONSORT flow diagram.

The author mentioned a sample size of 60, which is very small. Considering the Badan Pusat Statistik (2019) that was referred to in the introduction section (2), a larger sample size should have been selected for conducting this study. However, the information related to controlling the extraneous variables was not mentioned by the author because there is a greater probability of bias in quasi-experimental studies (3).

The author also mentioned that the youth health application education program was provided to the intervention group, and flipcharts educational content was provided to the control group. The concern here is, if both groups are provided with the same educational content, then how will the effectiveness be measured? Evidence suggests that in quasi-experimental research, there should be manipulation in one group and control in another group. Information was also not given on whether permission was taken to use the educational content as it is developed by the Ministry of Health. No information was given on the pre-testing/pilot study of questionnaires and the feasibility of youth health application and flipcharts educational contents. In addition, the process of implementing the youth health application and flipcharts educational content was missing.

In the results section, data given in table 2 are not as per the given descriptions and mean scores and P-values are missing.

Overall, much information is missing from the methodology, results, and discussion sections, and the given data are not correlating with the study descriptions. Thus, it was difficult to reach the outcome of the study.

References

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